

Olga MARUKHOVSKA-KARTUNOVA

*Associate Professor, Head of Social Sciences Section
of the Department of the of Foreign Languages
and General Education Disciplines,
University of Economics and Law "KROK",
Kyiv, Ukraine*

THE BEGINNING OF THE FORMATION OF SCIENCE-RESEARCH COMPETENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION STUDENTS IN THE COURSE "BASICS OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH"

Abstract. The relevance of the problem of the need to start forming science-research competence in applicants for the first (bachelor's) level of higher education of all specialties in the first or second year when writing the first course work is more than obvious. That is why it is imperative to introduce into the educational programs of all specialties a mandatory educational component called «Basics of Scientific Research» in the first or second year of bachelor's degree, depending on the year in which the first term paper is to be written and defended. The purpose of the article is to study the process of initiating the formation of science-research competence of higher education students in the first year of bachelor's degree and further development of this competence when writing a qualifying (bachelor's) thesis. This process of forming science-research competence can be continued in the master's and postgraduate programs when studying the mandatory educational component «Methodology and Organization of Scientific Research» by applicants of the second (master's) level and the third (educational and scientific) level of higher education.

Keywords: competency, competence, competency-based approach, research competence, science-research competence, basics of scientific research, research methodology, academic integrity.

Анотація. Актуальність проблеми необхідності започаткування формування науково-дослідницької компетентності у здобувачів першого (бакалаврського) рівня вищої освіти усіх спеціальностей на першому чи другому курсі при написанні першої курсової роботи більш ніж очевидна. Саме тому вкрай необхідно вводити в освітні програми усіх спеціальностей обов'язковий освітній компонент під назвою «Основи наукових досліджень» на першому чи другому курсі бакалаврату в залежності від того, на якому курсі під час навчання заплановано написання та захист першої курсової роботи. Метою статті є дослідження процесу започаткування формування науково-дослідницької компетентності здобувачів вищої освіти на перших курсах бакалаврату та подальший розвиток цієї компетентності при написанні кваліфікаційної (бакалаврської) роботи. Цей процес формування науково-дослідницької компетентності може бути продовжений в магістратурі та аспірантурі при вивченні обов'язкового освітнього компоненту «Методологія та організація наукових досліджень» здобувачами другого (магістерського) рівня та третього (освітньо-наукового) рівня вищої освіти.

Ключові слова: компетенція, компетентність, компетентнісний підхід, дослідницька компетентність, науково-дослідницька компетентність, основи наукових досліджень, методологія наукових досліджень, академічна доброчесність.

Statement of the problem and its relevance. The urgency of the problem of the need to start forming science-research competence in applicants for the first (bachelor's) level of higher education of all specialties in the first or second year when writing the first course work is more than obvious. That is why it is imperative to introduce such a mandatory educational component as «Basics of Scientific Research» into the educational programs of all specialties in order to teach it in the first or second year of a bachelor's degree, depending on which year

of study the first term paper is scheduled to be written and defended. The relevance of the study of the process of initiating the formation of science-research competence of higher education students in the first year of bachelor's degree directly affects the further development of this competence when writing a qualifying (bachelor's) thesis in the final year of bachelor's degree. This process of forming science-research competence is associated with important scientific and practical tasks and can be continued in the master's and postgraduate programs when studying the mandatory educational component «Methodology and Organization of Scientific Research» by applicants of the second (master's) level and the third (educational and scientific) level of higher education.

Analysis of key research and publications. Considerable attention to the problem of forming the science-research competence of higher education students is attracted by the variety of existing scientific publications of Ukrainian scientists. Thus, the issues of defining the concepts of «competency» and «competence» were dealt with in Ukraine by such scientists as: M. S. Golovan [1]; S. O. Kravchenko [2]; S. V. Leiko [3]; O. V. Tynkaliuk [4] and others.

The analysis of the main studies and publications devoted to the definition of the essence of these concepts, which are close in meaning, shows that most authors use the phrase «research competence» in their works: S. P. Arkhipova [5]; V. M. Gladkova [6]; M. S. Holovan, V. V. Yatsenko [7]; S. O. Kravchenko [8]; I. I. Kryvoruchko [9]; N. M. Lyubchak [10]; V. V. Fedorchuk [11] and others.

With regard to the definition of «science-research competence», in our opinion, the use of such a terminological phrase indicates that this is a new trend that has only recently appeared and began to spread in the scientific literature: M. O. Vinnik [12]; M. B. Yevtukh, L. L. Borysenko [13]; O. V. Prokhorova [14], etc.

The purpose of the article is to study the process of initiating the formation of science-research competence of higher education students in the first years of bachelor's degree and further development of this competence when writing a qualification (bachelor's) thesis.

To achieve the purpose of the study, the following general scientific **methods** were used: analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, systematization; competence-based approach, terminological and comparative and contrastive analysis to determine the essence and content of the main concepts of the study; structural and logical analysis, etc.

Presentation of the main material. Before analyzing the complex process of initiating the formation of science-research competence of applicants for the first (bachelor's) level of higher education, it is necessary to determine the essence of the three ascending concepts of «competency», «competence» and «science-research competence», which form the phrase of a qualitatively new scientific term «science-research competence».

First, it is necessary to clarify the definition and correlation of the concepts of «competency» and «competence». Thus, the concept of «competency» in the «New Explanatory Dictionary of the Ukrainian Language» is defined as «good knowledge of something», and the concept of «competent» as «having sufficient knowledge in any field; having good knowledge of something; understanding; based on knowledge; qualified» [15, p. 874].

In the works of Ukrainian scholars, sufficient attention is paid to the definition of the concepts of «competency» and «competence», but, in our opinion, the most successful and detailed analysis was made by the Ukrainian scholar M. S. Holovan in the article «Competency and competence: experience of theory, theory of experience», where a systematic analysis of these concepts was carried out: «competency is a certain norm, the achievement of which may

indicate the possibility of a correct solution to a task, and competence is an assessment of the achievement (or failure to achieve) of this norm»; «competence is the possession of competency..., it is an integrative formation of a personality that integrates knowledge, skills, abilities, experience and personal characteristics that determine the desire, ability and willingness to solve problems and tasks...; competence is a systemic concept that has its own structure, levels, functions, peculiar characteristics, properties; one can become competent by mastering certain competencies and realizing them in the experience of specific activities» [1, p. 24, 29].

Secondly, in accordance with the logic of the study, it is necessary to consider the interpretation and correlation of the concepts of «science-research competence» and «research competence». Regarding the problem of defining the essence of the concept of «research competence», according to N. M. Liubchak, «research competence» is a holistic, integrative quality of a personality which combines certain knowledge, skills, abilities and experience of a researcher and is manifested in the willingness and ability to carry out research activities with a view to obtaining new knowledge through the use of scientific cognition methods and the application of a creative approach. In the very nature of research competence there is a certain potential for professional self-development, professional career, and the research competence of a specialist is manifested in self-realization [10].

To this definition should be added the addition by S. O. Kravchenko that «research competence is manifested in the conscious readiness of a specialist to carry out active research activities, possessing a body of knowledge on the methodology and methods of scientific research; the ability to determine the essence, purpose, tasks, object and subject of research, formulate a working hypothesis, plan and conduct research, analyze the results, formulate conclusions; gain experience in preparing scientific publications, presentations and defense of research papers...» [8, c. 267].

From the scientific point of view, the most interesting is, first of all, the «clarified definition of «research competence» developed on the basis of theoretical analysis of scientific literature and proposed by the national scientist V. M. Gladkova as a set of: knowledge, research skills (a set of intellectual, practical and organizational skills), skills and research abilities (heuristics, creativity, intellectual mobility), etc. [6, c. 32].

Research competence is based on the knowledge, skills and abilities of higher education students to identify and formulate a specific scientific problem that can be the subject of their research, from writing an abstract or abstracts for a presentation at a scientific and practical conference in higher education institutions to writing coursework and qualifying bachelor's and master's theses at the first (bachelor's) and second (master's) levels of higher education, respectively. Possession of research competence enables higher education students to be able to comprehensively, systematically, creatively and critically process, implement and use the latest scientific information for research in the field of their educational and future professional activities in a particular field. These and many other knowledge and skills are provided by the study of the mandatory educational component «Basics of Scientific Research» to applicants for the first (bachelor's) level of higher education of all specialties in the first or second year when writing the first course work.

It is worth noting that the definition of the essence of the concept of «science-research competence» proposed by domestic scientists M. B. Yevtukh and L. L. Borysenko is of great scientific, theoretical and practical value: «We interpret the science-research competence of

future specialists as an integrative property of the individual that characterizes their readiness to solve research (problematic, educational, educational and professional...) tasks through the use of methods of scientific knowledge, independent search methods in goal setting, planning, ... making managerial decisions, which is expressed in the unity of value-motivational, cognitive and ... personal components» [13, p. 94–95].

Thus, the essence of the concept of « science-research competence» is much broader than the essence of the concept of « science-research competence», because it correlates with the field of research activities of a future specialist of any specialty.

An extremely important role in initiating the process of forming research and science-research competence in students of the first (bachelor's) level of higher education of all specialties should be played by the introduction of such a mandatory educational component as «Basics of Scientific Research» in educational programs in order to teach it in the first or second year of bachelor's degree, depending on which year of study is planned to write and defend the first course work. Based on my many years of teaching «Basics of Scientific Research» in the fourth year of a bachelor's degree before students write and defend their qualifying (bachelor's) thesis, I believe that it is extremely necessary to move it to the semester in which the curriculum schedules the writing and defense of the first term paper. This is necessary for higher education students to acquire theoretical knowledge and practical skills, general and professional competencies, as well as program learning outcomes contained in the content, core modules and topics of the proposed course. This educational component «Basics of Scientific Research» is proposed to be taught in two modules: The first theoretical module «Theoretical and Methodological Foundations of Scientific Research» and the second practical module «Methodological and Practical Basics of Preparing and Writing a Course and Qualification (Bachelor's) Paper».

In the process of teaching this compulsory educational component «Basics of Scientific Research», it is essential for students to reveal the essence of the main types and kinds of scientific research and scientific publications and their specificity in higher education; the content of the concept of method and methodology of scientific knowledge, as well as to characterize general scientific and special methods of scientific research. In addition, to start the process of developing science-research competence in higher education students, it is extremely important to analyze the writing algorithm, the main stages of creative work on the text of a scientific research and the general requirements for the introduction, structure, content and design of the work. They should be taught how to draw up a detailed plan, formulate the relevance, purpose, objectives, object, subject, and significance of the research topic, properly format the list of references in accordance with the current Standard, as well as citations, appendices, diagrams, tables, etc. All these acquired knowledge and skills will be further developed to form research competence, from writing a term paper to a qualifying (bachelor's) thesis. This process of further formation and improvement of science-research competence of higher education students can be continued in master's and postgraduate studies when studying the mandatory educational component «Methodology and Organization of Scientific Research» by students of the second (master's) level and the third (educational and scientific) level of higher education.

Conclusions and prospects for further research. The formation and improvement of science-research competence in students of all specialties at all levels of higher education is an ongoing process and one of the most urgent and important problems in higher education institutions. That is why it should become one of the leading priorities of the modern system of

higher education in our country, the solution of which requires significant efforts and measures of pedagogical, methodological and organizational nature. Therefore, the issues of defining and characterizing the main structural components of science-research competence, as well as the creation of an additional third module in the educational component «Basics of Scientific Research» dedicated to the urgent problem of ensuring that higher education students comply with academic integrity when writing research papers from term papers to qualification (bachelor's) and master's theses, remain relevant and require further attention in the future.

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